

Notes

Studies on 12-Heteropoly Niobotellurate

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ONLY a few heteropoly compounds of niobium have been reported^{1,2} in the literature. The present short communication deals with the preparation, characterisation and X-ray crystal diffraction studies of a new heteropoly compound containing tellurium as the hetero atom.

Water solutions of telluric acid and freshly prepared³ potassium hexaniobate, $K_7HNb_6O_{19} \cdot 13H_2O$, were taken in the molar ratio of 1:12, refluxed for two hours and then after leaving the solution in atmosphere for two days, it was finally crystallised under vacuum when small white needle shaped crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. The analysis of the compound was done by chemical and flame-photometric methods. The percentage of potassium, niobium and tellurium in the compound was found to be 11.87, 41.90, 4.75 against the theoretically calculated values 11.78, 42.09, 4.82 respectively. The percentage of water and oxygen, calculated by difference, came to 41.48. The individual estimations of hydrogen content in the compound came to 2.01 and hence the percentage of water was 18.20. From these percentage composition data, the compound has finally been represented as $K_8H_2[TeNb_{12}O_{88}] \cdot 27H_2O$ according to the views suggested by Lindqvist⁴.

X-ray crystallographic data and molecular weight determinations :

The unit cell dimensions were determined by using rotation and Weissenberg X-ray diffraction photograph for a single crystal of the compound. The crystal data were as follows :

$a=14.62$, $b=28.56$, $c=10.68$ Å⁰
 $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90$, hence the system is orthorhombic.

The volume V per unit cell was calculated to be 4459.404 Å³. The space group was uniquely established as $D^2_2h-P_{nnn}$ from the following systematic presence of reflections : hkl ; no condition, okl ; $k+l=2n$, hol ; $l+h=2n$, hko ; $h+k=2n$; hoo ; $(h=2n)$, oko ; $(k=2n)$, $00l$; $(l=2n)$ and hkl ; $h+k+l=2n$. The last condition gives the number of molecules per unit cell Z to be 2. The observed density, measured by floatation method, ρ_{obs} , was

found to be 1.96 gml⁻¹. From the relation $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66.M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound came to 2632.6, against the theoretical value 2648.53, which definitely concludes that the compound is monomeric.

References :

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Migration of Nonconductors (Iodine and Derivatives) during Electrolysis

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Though normally a non-conductor is supposed not to migrate while a current passes through a solution of the same, we have observed some nonconductors, particularly iodine and some of its compounds to have the remarkable property of electrical migration. The present preliminary note describes the salient features of such migration.

Experimental

The simplest way to observe such migration is to electrolyse an iodine solution in alcohol between two platinum electrodes in any U-tube (height 15 to 30 cm, diam. 20 to 35 mm) but a better way is as follows. To start with, the U-tube is filled up as shown in Fig 1A with the help of a pipette, and a D-C voltage of about 200 to 500 volts is applied between the electrodes. A current of a few hundred microamperes would pass through the solution. Methyl and ethyl alcohols (anhydrous and aqueous), glycols as also pyridine are the most convenient solvents to be used for such purpose.

Taking a typical case say iodine in absolute alcohol (its molar conductivity is more or less equal to that of a weak electrolyte such as acetic acid in

water) it would be seen in an hour or so of electrolysis that iodine is migrating to the anode. On continuing the current the final position becomes as shown in Fig 1B—which is the same as happens on continued electrolysis in a U-tube of almost any electrolyte (easily visible with potassium dichromate solutions)¹. On now reversing the current the iodine migrates to the new anode and a mirror image of Fig 1B is formed.

Fig. 1 A and B

Fig. 2.

It may be recalled that if a W-tube is used instead of a U-tube, dichromate solutions on electrolysis produce two stationary boundaries in the inside limbs¹. It is interesting to find that the same also happens with iodine solutions in alcohols, the solution demarcating itself into three sharply divided zones (deep brown/light brown/colourless) (i.e. double boundary formation) on prolonged electrolysis.

Such migration of a non-electrolyte is indeed remarkable but more remarkable is the fact that no gas liberation takes place during such electrolysis. As a matter of fact such current conduction can hardly be called electrolysis as it involves no lysis (i.e. decomposition) but is a mere transport of matter; in the same sense iodine can not be called an electrolyte. However, we shall continue to use the word electrolysis (and electrolyte) to include this type of electro-migration as a matter of convenience.

An easy way to observe the zero liberation of gas is to use an apparatus shown in Fig 2, which is a version of Hofmann apparatus used for class room demonstration of the composition of water in elementary teaching. The apparatus is filled with iodine solution. On using a M/2 solution, quite a heavy current (20-25 mA) may be sent through the solution using D.C. mains (220 volts). On sending the current overnight hardly any gas is found to get collected, though the coulometric value is well over one hundred cm³ of hydrogen at the cathode only. The only visible change would be a transport of

iodine from the cathode chamber to the anode chamber.

Besides elemental iodine iodoform in alcohol shows this behaviour in a striking way. Not only it migrates to the anode but it gets oxidised there so that the vicinity of the anode takes on the dark red appearance of iodine solution in a few hours of electrolysis. Some pale-coloured charge transfer complexes of iodine also show migration of iodine. Even the very strong cationic charge transfer complexes (light yellow) of iodine, say cetyl trimethyl ammonium salt-iodine complex, shows migration of iodine to the anode, though the complexation is generally supposed to be through the cation.

Theory: Any theory which involves H⁺ as the current carrier is untenable as no hydrogen gas is liberated. We have thought of two alternative theories complying with this condition. As electrons are pumped into the system through the cathode, some solvated electrons are produced. Since iodine forms a charge transfer complex with alcohol iodine being the acceptor, it is natural that the electron would pass from the solvent to the iodine molecules present. These I₂⁻ ions (or I₃⁻ ions formed by 3 I₂⁻ = 2 I₃⁻) then move to the anode.

The other theory is to assume that there is already an electron-transfer equilibrium of the type

and this gives the electrical mobility to the iodine. This is the counterpart of the conductivity of sodium solution in liquid ammonia except that there the solute donates the electron to the solvent whereas here the solvent does so to the solute but to a very minute extent.

If the first theory is correct, iodine solutions should show pronounced Hall effect whereas the second theory has no such implications. Besides, the first theory leads to a transport number of almost hundred per cent for iodine (after allowing for the solvent's share) whereas the second theory does not do so. Experiments are in progress to test these points as well as to find out other systems showing such unexpected property.

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Reference

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